

ABDULLA QAHHOR'S LIFE AND CREATIVE PATH AND HIS INFLUENCE ON UZBEK LITERATURE

Mingbojev Ibrokhim Alisher ugli

Student of Tashkent Institute of Finance, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

E-mail: mingbojevibrohim9@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807662>

Annotation: This article gathers information about Abdulla Kahhar, one of the bright figures of Uzbek literature, his life and creative path. Moreover, the most famous works written by the writer and their role in the development of Uzbek literature are highlighted.

Key words: Uzbek literature, Chagatai language, pre-existence, contribution, feuilletons, Uzbek warriors, patriotism, world literature, Uzbek translators.

Literature and art of Uzbekistan is called one of the bright and wonderful pages of the history of the world artistic culture. Along with Egypt and Mesopotamia, Greece and Rome, India and China, Central Asia laid the foundations of human civilization. The emergence of a cultural phenomenon in Uzbekistan is mainly due to its geographical location in the Central Asian Mesopotamia, where agricultural centers have been formed since ancient times. Uzbek literature refers to the literature produced and developed in the Republic of Uzbekistan with additional literary works contributed by the other parts of Afghanistan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan people of Central Asia. Influenced by the Russian and Turkish literature, Uzbek is predominantly written in Uzbek language with its roots in Chagatai language, one of the widely accessible languages in the region from 14th to 20th century. In Uzbek literature, Chagatai plays an important role as a reference to Central Asian literature, including Uzbekistan. The history of Uzbek literature spans between ancient and modern Uzbekistan. Before the founding of Uzbekistan, preceding colonies and the Russian conquest of Central Asia had significantly impacted Uzbek literature and continued to mark its presence until the Soviet Union was dissolved in 1991. Central Asian literature, including Uzbek is thus a part of Turkish and Russian literature. However, much of Uzbek literature witnessed significant development in modern era due to its pre-existence in Uzbeks. There were a lot of famous and creative writers who strongly influence on development of Uzbek literature. Abdulla Kahhar was one of them.

Abdulla Kahhar, who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature, was born on September 1907, 17 in Kokand in a family of blacksmiths. Abdulla received his secondary education in Kokand and came to Tashkent in 1925 to work for the Red Uzbekistan newspaper. He studied at the Pedagogical Faculty of the Central Asian State Medical University (1930). The writer was the executive secretary of the magazine "Soviet Literature" and the editor of the State Publishing House of Uzbekistan (1954-1956). Abdulla Qahhor's work dates back to 1924[1]. Initially, his stories, feuilletons and reports were published in the magazine "Mushtum", in the newspapers "Yangi Fergana" and "Kyzyl Uzbekistan". The author's first collection of short stories, The World Lives, was published in 1938. In the 30s, the author's collections of "Stories" (1935, 1938, 1939) came into the hands of readers. During this period, Abdulla Kahhar wrote the novel Sarob (1935) in addition to short stories.

During the war years, the author published several feuilletons, essays and short stories. Stories such as "Asror bobo", "Dardaqdan qakhramon", "Kampirlar sim qoqdi", "Khotinlar" and "Oltin yulduz" express the courage of Uzbek warriors, hard work and high patriotism of our people.

The author's novel "Koshchinor Lights" (1951), created in the post-war years, is devoted to the theme of collectivization. He made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek drama with his comedies "Shahi sozana" (1951), "Painful teeth" (1954), "Sound from the coffin" (1962), "My grandparents" (1967). Especially in the poem "Shahi sozana" the playwright masterfully covered the topic of protection and development of gray lands[2]. Pesa has been successfully performed on the stages of our republic and a number of foreign countries. The author's short stories "Sinchalak" (1958), "Love" (1968), "Fairy tales from the past" (1965) made an important contribution to the development of Uzbek prose. He wrote Oybek ("Childhood") for the story "Fairy Tales from the Past", N. Among the autobiographical stories of such writers as Safarov ("What I saw and experienced"), he was awarded the State Prize named after Hamza.

Uzbek readers translated by Abdulla Kahhar M. Gorky's "My dorilfununlarim", I. V. Gogol's "Inspector", L. N. They managed to read Tolstoy's novel "War and Peace" (books I - II) and a number of other works in their native languages. Abdulla Kahhar was awarded the title of People's Writer of Uzbekistan for his services in the field of literature (1967). He died on May 1968, 25 in Moscow at the age of 61. He was posthumously awarded the Order of Merit (2000)[3]. Qahhor's stories Asror bobo (Grandpa Asror), Dardaqdan chiqqan qahramon (A Hero from Dardaqa), Kampirlar sim qoqdi (Old Women Rang), Xotinlar (Women), and Oltin yulduz (The Golden Star) depict the courage of Uzbek soldiers and the hard work of Uzbek workers during the Soviet-German war against Nazi Germany and its allies. Qahhor's other novels and stories include Sarob (Mirage) (1935), O'g'ri (The Thief) (1936), Bemor (The Patient) (1936), Qo'shchinor chiroqlari (The Lights of Qo'shchinor) (1951), O'tmishdan ertaklar (Stories from the Past) (1965), Muhabbat (Love) (1968), Mahalla, Millatchilar (Nationalists), and others. He is also known for his plays Shohi so'zana (Silk Suzani) (1950), Og'riq tishlar (Hurting Teeth) (1950), Tobutdan tovush (A Sound from the Coffin) (1962), and Ayajonlarim (My Dear Mothers) (1967). He translated the works of many Russian writers, such as Alexander Pushkin, Anton Chekhov, and Nikolai Gogol into the Uzbek language. In particular, he translated The Captain's Daughter of Pushkin, Marriage and The Government Inspector of Gogol, and, together with his wife Kibriyo Qahhorova, War and Peace of Leo Tolstoy[4].

In conclusion we should highlighted that Abdulla Kahhar influenced many Uzbek writers, including Said Ahmad, O'tkir Hoshimov, and Erkin Vohidov. His outstanding translations of the works of many great Russian and foreign writers into the Uzbek language enabled Uzbek readers to enjoy the masterpieces of world literature in their own language. Many Uzbek translators of literary works have used Kahhar's work as a benchmark.

References:

1. Nigina Ergasheva (23 August 2007). "For Abdulla Kahhar's 100th anniversary". Uzbeksitan Today. Archived from the original on 20 March 2011. Retrieved 3 February 2012.
2. "The Abdulla Kahhar Museum". Retrieved 3 February 2012.

3. "Abdulla Kahhar". Ensiklopedik lug'at (in Uzbek). Vol. 1. Toshkent: O'zbek sovet ensiklopediyasi. 1988. pp. 5-6. 5-89890-002-0.
4. "Abdulla Kahhar (1907-1968)". Ziyouz (in Uzbek). Retrieved 16 September 2014.

